

Pleuropericardial Window for the Management of Combined Pleural and Pericardial Effusions A Retrospective Single-Center Analysis

Author: Anastasia-Parascheva Sandu¹

Co-authors: Ana-Isabela Dobrin¹, Catherine-Teodora Costan¹, Ioana Tudorache¹

Coordinator: Cristian Sandu²

Affiliations:

¹ *Faculty of Medicine, “Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iasi, Romania*

² *Regional Institute of Oncology, Iasi, Romania*

Introduction

Combined pericardial and pleural effusions represent a complex clinical condition, frequently associated with oncological disease, but also encountered in non-malignant settings. These cases may lead to significant symptoms and, in severe situations, to cardiac tamponade, thus requiring prompt and effective management.

Materials and Methods

We performed a retrospective analysis of patients treated for pericardial effusion at the Regional Institute of Oncology Iasi over a 5-year period. A total of 19 patients were included. Clinical presentation, underlying pathology, imaging findings, and perioperative data were analyzed. The surgical technique consisted of a pleuropericardial window performed via thoracotomy or video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS).

Results

Dyspnea was the most common presenting symptom. The underlying pathology was predominantly malignant, with bronchopulmonary cancer being the most frequent diagnosis (6 patients), followed by other oncological and non-malignant etiologies. Pleural effusion was present in 9 patients, while 5 presented with cardiac tamponade requiring urgent intervention. Notably, 12 patients had not received preoperative chemotherapy, suggesting that treatment-related factors were unlikely to represent the main trigger for effusion development. The procedure enabled effective drainage of pericardial fluid into the pleural cavity and allowed tissue sampling for diagnostic purposes. No significant postoperative complications were recorded. Survival beyond one year was observed in 4 patients.

Conclusion

Pleuropericardial window is a safe and effective therapeutic option in patients with symptomatic pericardial effusion, particularly when associated pleural involvement is present. It ensures durable fluid control and facilitates diagnostic assessment. Based on existing literature, this approach may provide better local control compared with drainage-only techniques. Careful patient selection remains essential.

Keywords

VATS, cardiac tamponade, pleural effusion